

Pagodas of Portuguese Goa

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Connecting spots between Goan Hindus and Portugueses from 16th century, the Pagodes were the former Hindu temples, named by Hindus as Devulla or Vimana. Under Portuguese rule were transformed into targets of Catholic missionary persecution, many being destroyed, becoming places of tension and dispute. Thus, in this entry we are going to present this religious places by the Luso-Hindu concept of the Pagode.

Date Range: 1510 CE - 1600 CE

Region: Goa

Region tags: India, Konkani, Goa

Goa before Portuguese conquer belonged to the Bijapur Sultanate, serving as a trade port connected to the Arabian and Persian market. After 1510 the island of Tisvadi, where the city is located, began to be modeled as the Portuguese politics demanded. Its architecture and space shapping were elaborated to create an "Asian Lisbon", what could be also seen in its political powers. Governed by a Viceroy, containing important and powerful Portuguese institutions and made to be a Catholic fortress, Goa was an important place of the Modern Europeans affairs in Orient.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: <https://www.historia.uff.br/stricto/td/1582.pdf>
- Source 2: https://books.google.com.br/books/about/The_Hindu_Temple.html?id=NNcXrBI19S0C&redir_esc=y
- Source 3: <https://journals.openedition.org/lerhistoria/1899>

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://asigoacircle.gov.in/monument/>

– Source 1 Description: Mahadev Temple, Tambdisurla: dedicated to the god Shiva, it is maybe the only intact temple/ pagode that survived the Portuguese and, before, Muslim attacks against Hindu temples. Dated to the 13th century it is related to the Goa-Kadamba dynasty. The temple consists of Garbhagriha (sanctum), Antara (vestibule) and Nandi Mandapa (pillared hall) and is built of chlorite schist. The Mandapa has balustrade entrances on three sides with Kakshana arrangement.

– Source 2 URL: <http://asigoacircle.gov.in/monument/>

– Source 2 Description: "Rock Cut Caves, Arvalim: excavated in laterite hill consisting of two major caves and a residential chamber at the south east end, the cave excavation are running continuously and divided by thin rock cut walls, facing south west. The caves are provided with couple of steps leading to an open courtyard which in turn reach into a pillared front hall or Ardhamandapa. From where, entrance steps lead into the cave shrines. There is a Brahmi inscription datable to early 7th century A.D". Cf.: <http://asigoacircle.gov.in/monument/>

– Source 3 URL: <http://asigoacircle.gov.in/monument/>

– Source 3 Description: Excavated site, Chandor: This is located on the Kushavati river and has been identified as the ancient city of Chandrapur, which served as a capital for the Bhojas and up to Kadambas (4th to 11th Century A. D.), besides as a port town. The site was subjected to excavation in 1930's, 1975 and in 2000-03.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 20th century and first decade of 21st century

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Archaeological Survey of India - Goa Circle

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Cave

Reference: Stella Kramrisch. *The Hindu Temple* (vol. 1 and 2). Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers. isbn: 81-208-0223-3.

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Reference: Stella Kramrisch. The Hindu Temple. Motilal Banarsidass Publ.. isbn: 9788120802230.

↳ Type of feature

– Mound

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: There was not a single feature in the composition of the Pagodes. Those which can be understood as temples were built together with expressive changes in the place where they were erected, such as water tanks and ritual clearing of the area.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Thinking the Pagode as a Portuguese term to define Hindu "religious" building, altar, sacred image or shrine, these places, understood approximately as one general thing (in Catholic Portuguese comprehension about Hindu sacred places and images), is possible, thus, to affirm that it was composed by many structures throughout different moments.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Thinking the Pagode as a Portuguese term to define Hindu "religious" building, altar, sacred image or shrine, these places, understood approximately as one general thing (in Catholic Portuguese comprehension about Hindu sacred places and images), is possible, thus, to affirm that it was composed by many structures throughout different moments.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Pagodes, in Portuguese perspective, could be either idols, altars or temples. Because of that some of them were part of temples or be the temple and sanctuary itself.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Many Pagodes were destructed by the Portugueses in the Sixteenth century. Those wich were temples, after being demolished, had its space and lands used by the Portuguese Church, constructing there Catholic temples, monasteries and religious schools.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: By Portuguese initiative, the Hindu temples were destroyed by soldiers at Vicerroy and Church service. The destruction perpetrated could be executed using fire at first, followed by total demolishing of the Pagode.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: Before Portuguese presence in Goa, many temples, idols and altars were destroyed by Muslim forces. Under the power of Bijapur Sultanate, for example, many manifestations of Hindu beliefs, rites and costumes were persecuted by Muslim forces in the island.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Some temples were reconstructed in Goa in other places. Many of those ones claim that they are the heirs of the old Pagodes destroyed by the Portugueses in the Sixteenth century. Cf.: http://shreeshantadurga.com/history_temple.asp ; <http://shantadurgakunkalikarin.org/spiritualfacts.htm> .

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Each Pagode were dedicated to a particular deity of Hindu pantheon. In Goa, for example, many of them were dedicated to deities from Vedic traditions or to its local manifestations, such as Shanta Durga. However, under Portuguese rule, those Hindu manifestations were interpreted as satanic cults, wich were structured in the former Hindu religious spaces and groups.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Pagodes, in its form of temples, though could be dedicated to a higher deity, received manifestations of other Hindu gods related to the main one.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Member of castes dedicated to masonry, building and craftsmanship.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

– Revealed by high god

Notes: According to mythological history of the Pagodes in form of temples, it is not rare the narrative of a god or goddess presenting to a member of local Hindu community his or her wish to "live" in some specific place. Following the god or goddess will, its followers build altars or temples attending to his or her desire.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– I don't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: One non-rare reason to build a Pagode in form of temple to a deity was the

manifestation of his or her will, through the dreams of a member of local Hindu community who is member of his or her cult, to "live" in specific places. To follow the god or goddess desire, Hindu communities in Goa built temples to honor their deity's wish.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: Though the temples Pagodes were not built to house sacred texts, many of them served as archives to different kinds of religious and administrative texts.

Reference: Toetónio R. de Souza. Goa Medieval. Lisboa: Editorial Estampa. isbn: 972-33-0943-2.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Portuguese Goa pagodes, as other hindu temples wich construction were based on temple building classical tractates, such as the Vastushastra and the Vishnudharmottara, were located near lakes and rivers. Many of them, following the instructions present in that literature, built also artificial ponds and tanks called prakara to correspond to the protocols and ideal practices imposed to the important work of constructing temples.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Besides the central sanctuary, called devulla in sanskrit, South India temples, such as the Goan ones, used to be surrounded by walls. These walls, in southern temples, had gates located in the four cardinal points, and in each gate there was a tower called gopuran. Gopurans were formed by many levels decorated with many gods and goddesses images. Portuguese Goan pagodes, however, doesn't show the gopurans over its gates. They used to have a Deepmal, or "Lamps Tower", located in the yard around the main temple. Chapels destined to minor deities, prakara (ponds) and buildings used as dormitories by the peregrines were also present in the pagode's areas.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: At southern Hindu temples, including Portuguese Goa pagodes, status differences are recognizable amid the strucutres wich composed the whole area identified as a Hindu temple. Higher in Hindu sacred buildings hierarchy was the devulla, the main temple, where was located the idol of the greater deity of the pagode. At the entrance of the main temple was the naubat khana, a little tower where musicians played himns to the deities. Placed

around the yard where was located, at its centre, the devulla, were the chapels dedicated to minor gods and goddesses associated to the higher god or goddess worshiped at the greater sanctuary.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: The monument structure present in Portuguese Goan pagodes was the Deepmal, the "Tower of Lamps". Its features could vary from a pagode to another, including the area it could occupy inside the pagode's area and its height.

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: The monument structure present in Portuguese Goan pagodes was the Deepmal, the "Tower of Lamps". Its features could vary from a pagode to another, including the area it could occupy inside the pagode's area and its height.

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The monument structure present in Portuguese Goan pagodes was the Deepmal, the "Tower of Lamps". Its features could vary from a pagode to another, including the area it could occupy inside the pagode's area and its height.

Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The monument structure present in Portuguese Goan pagodes was the Deepmal, the "Tower of Lamps". Its features could vary from a pagode to another, including the area it could occupy inside the pagode's area and its height.

Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The monument structure present in Portuguese Goan pagodes was the Deepmal, the "Tower of Lamps". Its features could vary from a pagode to another, including the area it could occupy inside the pagode's area and its height.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Though the majority of the materials used to build the pagodes were found in Goa as in its hinterlands, the materials used to create the idols could include imported gems and precious metals.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: All the raw materials used to build the pagodes were previously manipulated in order to

adapt them to the construction. Rocks, wood, clay and fibers were tooled and elaborated to fit into the temple building necessities.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Portuguese Goa devullas were considered by hindus the home of the gods or goddesses who were worshipped there. Characteristic present in general in Hindu temples, the specific site where the god remained was called murti. There, its image was venerated. To see the image of the god or goddess was considered a sacred moment, called darshan. Around the image were present offerings given by its worshippers.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: I don't know.
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cult statues:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
 - Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Following researches about the pagodes located in the portion of Goa called "Novas Conquistas", "New Conquerings" (area conquered by the Portugueses in the XVIII century), it is possible to affirm that the temples of Velha Goa use to have reliefs decorating its inner pillars. As those Nova Conquista temples were, in many cases, the fleeting ones from Velha Goa (fugue occasioned by Catholic persecution in the XVI century), its rebuilding used the aesthetical features that they used to have in their original locations. Therefore, as the Nova Conquista pagodes survived through centuries, is possibel to deduce how they were in Old Goa. One of its main features were its pllars decorated with reliefs, wich, in few cases, survived the Catholic persecution and were transplanted to the new sites in Novas Conquistas.

Reference: Pedro Pombo. Goan Temple Architecture: Embodying Landscape and History.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: I Don't know.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due the destruction of pagodes in Old Goa at the XVI century, it is very difficult to know if there were paintings inside them.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due the destruction of pagodes in Old Goa at the XVI century, it is very difficult to know if there were mosaics inside them.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Though there was not an unique supreme god in hindu traditions, there was among Portuguese Goa Hindu community two main cults. One, the Shaiva, cult considered Shiva as the higher god. The other, called Vaishnava, considered Vishnu occupying the position of higher god. Both cults maintained mythological and ritual relations with minor god and goddesses present in Goan Hindu traditions.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Though the supreme Shaiva or Vaishnava god does not communicate with its worshippers at the temple, this place was considered its house. Its presence was concentrated in its sacred statue, located in the most important site inside the temple.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: In the case of Hindu temples, the god was visible in the form of its statue, located in the most important site inside the temple. The worshippers allowed to be close to this statue (capacity related to the position of the worshipper in caste system) executed the darshan, a personal ritual which consisted basically in see the god incarnated in its statue.

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: The statue was visible to those worshippers who belonged to the castes authorized to enter at the most important site of the temple, where was located the statue

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: At the Puja ritual, executed inside the temple, the statue of the god was bathed, adorned with jewels, clothes, flowers and necklaces. This offerings could be very valuable.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Coconut and betel offerings were made as part of the Puja in Goan Hindu temples. In Portuguese sources about this Hindu religious practice it is shown as "quebrar cocos", wich means "to break coconuts". This ritual was made as an important sacrifice among Goan Hindu communities, being the coconut an important fruit to its local economy.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: The Jatti (the caste system) instituted ritual functions to each one of its groups. The mandatory character of the execution of rituals was a consequence of the respect the Jatti and life itself in order to preserv the life itself.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The temples (devulla in sanskrit, pagode in Portuguese) were the final destiny of Hindu pilgrimages, specially those built in Ayodhia, Mathura, Maya, Kashi, Avantika and Dvaravati. Suposing that the pagodes of Goa were built under the rules of the Hindu sacred architectural treatises, its location may have been considered auspicious. After all, Goa is an island, what is considered in that treatises, due the abundant presence of water, an auspicious land. Portuguese sources indicate a great number of pagodes in the main island and in the minor ones, as well as the presence of Hindu pilgrims that arrived from time to time to Goan temples.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: The festivals followed the traditional calendars related to the god or goddess homage by its worshippers in this occasion.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field doesn't know.

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– I don't know

Divination through human communication:

– I don't know

Divination through animal-behavior:

– I don't know

Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: In Shantadurga pagodes, its worshippers used to place petals in both sides of its statue. A question has to be made, wich answer would be given by goddess following the order of the falling of the petals.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The Ratha-Yatra (procession) festivals began at the temple, where teh god or goddess statue was prepared to go outside the "pagode". Once ready, the statue was carried in adorned charriots, carried by its officiants and other worshippers. Along the statue procession, music was played and ceremonies were executed among many Hindu people following the charriot.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Puja and prasad were two small-scale rituals executed inside the temple. The first consisted in offerings to the god or goddess who were worshiped at the "pagode". The second consisted in the concession of blessings by the god or goddess to its worshipers. In Goa, the Prasad had other feature: divination. This practice usually was associated to the cult of Shantadurga.

Reference: Eduardo Nogueira. *Pagodes do Diabo. Sociedade e Religião Hindu na Goa Portuguesa (c.1510-c.1560)*. Niterói: Universidade Federal Fluminense.

Reference: XAVIER Ângela Barreto. *A invenção de Goa. Poder imperial e conversões culturais nos séculos XVI e XVII..* Lisbon: Imprensa de Ciências Sociais. isbn: 978-972-671-209-1.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: The periodicity of the rituals followed the traditional calendars associated to each god or goddess worshipped.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes

Notes: Bottos were the officiants of Hindu rituals inside the pagodes. These rites should be executed everyday by the bottos, who lived in the domains of the pagode, being sustained by the offerings and by the cultivation of the land that belonged to the temple. The bavinias, virgin women who assisted the rituals and were responsible of the cleaning of the pagode, washing the god or goddess statue and preserving the illumination of the temple, also dwelled in the temple domains. Also living around the main pagode were the women called calavantas, dancers and singers who dedicated their lives to the god or goddess worshipped. They were accompanied by the bazanterys and the deusis, who were musicians. Other servers, as carpenters, blacksmiths and cleaners (the last ones belonging to the lower castes) also lived in the lands of the temple, working on its maintenance.

- ↳ Present part time
 - No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes

Notes: The bottos were men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Bottos belonged to the Brahmin caste.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Around the main pagode there were living spaces to its priests and servers. The temple lands were also disponsible to be cultivated by its inhabitants.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Notes: There was not an institution to maintain the pagode, although there were servers formally attached to it working on its maintenance.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Notes: The mahajans were ganvkars (Hindu land lords) responsible for the temple administration. They had to provide with means and land to the construction of the pagode and were in charge of its repairing. They had also the power to concede the best lands to the bottos and to reward the temple servers for their work.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The pagode were the owners of lands, called nelly, considered the best lands in the region of Goa.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: The lands around the temple (called prakara lands) served as the location of regular fairs. The temples also served as the tax archives of the villages where they were located. Meetings to resolve properties disputes were executed in the domains of the pagode. Gatherings of the village council (called ganvkari) took place around sacred trees located in the pagodes lands. Primary education of the children who lived in the village where the pagode was located also was executed in the pagode.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

↳ Function for water management:

– I don't know

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Tax archives were kept inside the temple under the management of the Servi-Sarasvat Brahmins.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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